

STAGES OF TEACHING THE GENETIC CONSISTENCY OF SUBSTANCES FROM CHEMISTRY

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Abstract. The article presents information about the approaches, models, role of chemical experiment and its principles used in the study of genetic consistency of chemical compounds.

Key words: *genetic consistency, landmark, structural-structural, personal-activity, integrative, contextual approach;*

In the science of chemistry, studying the genetic consistency between substances in a sequence, studying the concept of "genetic consistency" to determine the stages of formation of one substance into another is one of the important tasks. This was the starting point for determining effective ways of improving the methodology of forming the concept of "genetic consistency".

We used the theory of step-by-step formation of mental actions, systematic-structural, personal-activity, integrative, contextual approaches as methodological guidelines for the process of forming the concept of "genetic consistency".

The formation of chemical concepts should be carried out in the following direction: chemical experiment → observation → creating a mental image of micro-objects — a material model → a marked model. The criterion of truth should be not the words of the teacher, not the textbook, not the logic of thinking, but the experiment.

The methodology and the subsystem of the school chemical experiment are based on two principles: didactic and original groups. Their construction, in turn, is based on the following principles of education: scientificity and openness, systematicity and stability, the connection of education with life, the visibility, consciousness and activity of students, education with the leading role of the teacher. -strength, awareness and effectiveness of educational and developmental outcomes. We will consider the most important of them:

1. The principle of scientificity of education, which is interpreted as a requirement to pay equal attention to the theory and method of science. At the same time, the first is conditionally related to scientific knowledge, and the second is related to practical skills and abilities in solving the problems studied by this science. A school chemistry course can combine induction and deduction

with a gradual increase in the proportion of deduction by providing an effective link between the empirical and the theoretical. The study of classes of organic compounds is carried out deductively based on the theory of the structure of organic compounds. Observations and chemical experiments take the leading place in proving the basic rules of chemistry during the educational process.

2. The principle of the priority of the method of knowledge or the origin of the method of teaching a particular subject from its method of knowledge. If observation and experiment play an important role in natural science, learning these sciences cannot be imagined without using these methods.

3. The principle of clarity. Regarding our problem of revealing the genetic relationships between inorganic and organic compounds, as well as the idea of the development of chemistry, the role of chemical experiment as one of the visualization tools is of great importance. Knowing the rules of forming chemical equations and the chemical properties of chemical compounds, the student, without any special feelings, carries out the chain of transformations proposed by the teacher or even created by him.

But its practical implementation leaves an unforgettable impression, because often through simple changes, the student learns more and more new substances belonging to different classes of compounds, different in terms of color, smell, and physical state. What is indicated by the arrows in the "chain" suddenly "comes to life" and becomes a controlled reality, which indeed confirms the genetic connection of different classes of chemical compounds.

4. The principle of sustainability. The proposed system using the school chemical experiment is built on one of the main principles of education - the principle of consistency. The concepts of "system" and "systematic approach" are widely used in science. Philosophical aspects of the development of the general theory of systems, coherence and systematic approach are revealed, and any system is characterized by a number of unique features.

Here we consider the principles that are considered the main ones in relation to the subsystem of the chemical experiment:

1. Integrity. The properties of this system cannot be fundamentally reduced to the sum of the properties of its constituent elements and cannot be derived from the final properties of the whole; the dependence of each element, the properties and relations of the system on their place and functions in the whole unit. A chemical experiment is a whole system consisting of various types and forms, each of which performs its own functions.

2. Systematicity. Systemicity is the ability to describe a system by establishing a "web of connections and relationships" so that a set of elements becomes a connected whole, where each element is ultimately related to all other elements. emerges, and its properties cannot be understood without considering this connection" [4].

Based on the classification of organic compounds, finding the main blocks of the studied classes and the relationships between them, the features of the structure of our system were revealed on the basis of chemical experiments.

3. Hierarchy. Each component of the system, in turn, can be considered a subsystem.

The subsystem of the proposed chemical experiment is a component of a more complex model for the formation of the studied definition. In turn, in the subsystem of a chemical experiment, we distinguish smaller components - its various types and forms of organization.

4. The abundance of definitions. Due to the inherent complexity of each system, its adequate knowledge requires the construction of many different models, each of which describes only a certain aspect of the system.

In our research, we propose a system based on chemical experience and a model for forming the concept of genetic relationships of organic compounds based on it.

5. Interdependence of the system and the environment. Being the leading active component of interaction, the system forms and manifests its properties in the process of interaction with the environment. Our proposed system helps to purposefully form not only this concept, but also a number of other fundamental definitions of the course of organic chemistry and, in turn, the block of chemical, psychological, pedagogical, and methodological knowledge of students.

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